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SURVEY OF MACHINE TRANSLATION SYSTEMS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The work in the area of machine translation has been going on for last few decades but the promising translation work began in the early 1990s due to advanced research in Artificial Intelligence and Computational Linguistics. India is a multilingual and multicultural country with over 1.25 billion population and 22 constitutionally recognized languages which are written in 12 different scripts. This necessitates the automated machine translation system for English to Indian languages and among Indian languages so as to exchange the information amongst people in their local language. Many usable machine translation systems have been developed and are under development in India and around the world. The paper focuses on different approaches used in the development of Machine Translation Systems and also briefly described some of the Machine Translation Systems along with their features, domains and limitations.

KEYWORDS

Machine Translation, Example-based MT, Transfer-based MT, Interlingua-based MT

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RULE BASED TRANSLITERATION SCHEME FOR ENGLISH TO PUNJABI

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ABSTRACT

Machine Transliteration has come out to be an emerging and a very important research area in the field of machine translation. Transliteration basically aims to preserve the phonological structure of words. Proper transliteration of name entities plays a very significant role in improving the quality of machine translation. In this paper we are doing machine transliteration for English-Punjabi language pair using rule based approach. We have constructed some rules for syllabification. Syllabification is the process to extract or separate the syllable from the words. In this we are calculating the probabilities for name entities (Proper names and location). For those words which do not come under the category of name entities, separate probabilities are being calculated by using relative frequency through a statistical machine translation toolkit known as MOSES. Using these probabilities we are transliterating our input text from English to Punjabi.

KEYWORDS

Machine Translation, Machine Transliteration, Name entity recognition, Syllabification

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Hybrid Part-Of-Speech Tagger for Non-Vocalized Arabic Text

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ABSTRACT

Part of speech tagging (POS tagging) has a crucial role in different fields of natural language processing (NLP) including Speech Recognition, Natural Language Parsing, Information Retrieval and Multi Words Term Extraction. This paper proposes an efficient and accurate POS Tagging technique for Arabic language using hybrid approach. Due to the ambiguity issue, Arabic Rule-Based method suffers from misclassified and unanalyzed words. To overcome these two problems, we propose a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) integrated with Arabic Rule-Based method. Our POS tagger generates a set of three POS tags: Noun, Verb, and Particle. The proposed technique uses the different contextual information of the words with a variety of the features which are helpful to predict the various POS classes. To evaluate its accuracy, the proposed method has been trained and tested with two corpora: the Holy Quran Corpus and Kalimat Corpus for undiacritized Classical Arabic language. The experiment results demonstrate the efficiency of our method for Arabic POS Tagging. In fact, the obtained accuracies rates are 97.6%, 96.8% and 94.4% for respectively our Hybrid Tagger, HMM Tagger and for the Rule-Based Tagger with Holy Quran Corpus. And for Kalimat Corpus we obtained 94.60%, 97.40% and 98% for respectively Rule-Based Tagger, HMM Tagger and our Hybrid Tagger.

KEYWORDS

Part-Of-Speech Tagger, Natural Language Applications, Natural Language Parsing, Hidden Markov Model, Multi Words Term Extraction, Speech Recognition.

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HINDI AND MARATHI TO ENGLISH MACHINE TRANSLITERATION USING SVM

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ABSTRACT

Language transliteration is one of the important areas in NLP. Transliteration is very useful for converting the named entities (NEs) written in one script to another script in NLP applications like Cross Lingual Information Retrieval (CLIR), Multilingual Voice Chat Applications and Real Time Machine Translation (MT). The most important requirement of Transliteration system is to preserve the phonetic properties of source language after the transliteration in target language. In this paper, we have proposed the named entity transliteration for Hindi to English and Marathi to English language pairs using Support Vector Machine (SVM). In the proposed approach, the source named entity is segmented into transliteration units; hence transliteration problem can be viewed as sequence labeling problem. The classification of phonetic units is done by using the polynomial kernel function of Support Vector Machine (SVM). Proposed approach uses phonetic of the source language and n-gram as two features for transliteration..

KEYWORDS

Machine Transliteration, n-gram, Support Vector Machine, Syllabification.

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GENETIC APPROACH FOR ARABIC PART OF SPEECH TAGGING

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ABSTRACT

With the growing number of textual resources available, the ability to understand them becomes critical. An essential first step in understanding these sources is the ability to identify the parts-of-speech in each sentence. Arabic is a morphologically rich language, which presents a challenge for part of speech tagging. In this paper, our goal is to propose, improve, and implement a part-of-speech tagger based on a genetic algorithm. The accuracy obtained with this method is comparable to that of other probabilistic approaches.

KEYWORDS

Part-of-Speech Tagging, Genetic algorithm, Natural Language Processing, Part-of-Speech tagger, Tagset, Training tables & corpus

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